

Appendix B: Additional plots

In this section, we report some additional plots.

In Fig. B.1 we give the velocity dispersion as function of stellar mass $\sigma(m)$ for the analyzed GCs, without NGC 6397 (given in Fig. 1), with the best-fit model as output of the first fitting procedure, described in Sect. 3.1, that takes the mass function slopes of GCs from Baumgardt et al. (2023) and constrain Φ_0 and σ_0 from W22 projected dispersion data. It is also shown the fit result with the Bianchini fitting function. The respective parameters are in Table 1.

In Fig. B.2 we show the contour plots obtained for the same GCs, following our second approach of introducing the mass function slope to the parameter space (Sect. 3.2).

In Fig. B.3 we report the SBPs obtained for each GC without NGC 6341 (given in Fig. 10), by fitting Trager et al. (1995) data with the model prediction as described in Sect. 2.2.2, by assuming the mass function slopes from Baumgardt et al. (2023), BaSTI isochrones (Hidalgo et al. 2018; Pietrinferni et al. 2021; Salaris et al. 2022; Pietrinferni et al. 2024) at 13 Gyr, with $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.4$, $Y = 0.247$ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from the Harris catalog. It is important to note that the data from Trager et al. (1995) are a collection of heterogeneous observations, and some clusters have multiple values for the same radial coordinate, also showing different trends. This likely degrades the quality of the fit and may lead to inaccurate values for the parameters. For example, while the high value of the normalized χ^2 for NGC 104 and NGC 5904 can be related to small uncertainties in the data points, NGC 6397 clearly has multiple data trends (see Fig. B.3). Consequently, not only we get a large χ^2 value, but also the estimated core radius is an order of magnitude larger than that from the Harris catalog. This suggests that the points with smaller errors in the inner region are more reliable, which is also confirmed by the SBP by Noyola & Gebhardt (2006), which looks more regular in the region $R < 10^2$ arcsec. Thus, for this cluster our fitting procedure is not reliable and needs to be repeated by increasing the quality of the data, such as changing the cut-off value for w_i and including the data from Noyola & Gebhardt (2006). Furthermore, it must be considered that NGC 6397 is a post-core-collapse object, for which King-like models are not appropriate in describing the structure of the system, especially in the inner regions.

Finally, Fig. B.4 gives the relation between the $\sigma(m)$ relative error on data against our χ^2 value, while Fig. B.5 underlines how the predicted velocity dispersion as function of the mass tends to the equipartition limit $\sigma(m) \propto m^{-1/2}$ for increasing values of Φ_0 .

Fig. B.1: Velocity dispersion as function of stellar mass for the analyzed clusters (without NGC 6397 given in Sect. 3.1). The error bars are the binned data from Watkins et al. (2022), the continuous green line is our best-fit with the Bianchini et al. (2016) fitting function with its error band, the dotted brown line is the equipartition limit and the dashed orange line is our model best-fit assuming Baumgardt et al. (2023) mass function slope, with its confidence band. Estimated parameters are given in Table 1.

Fig. B.2: Contour plots for analyzed GCs (without NGC 6397 given in the main text) in the Φ_0 - α plane showing the χ^2 levels. The blue band gives the slope from Baumgardt et al. (2023). Squares indicate locations around the χ^2 minimum, identified by a big gray circle.

Fig. B.3: Surface brightness profiles for the analyzed clusters (without NGC 6341 given in Sect. 3.5). The dots with error bars are the data from Trager et al. (1995) analyzed following the work by McLaughlin & van der Marel (2005) and Zocchi et al. (2012). The continuous blue line is our model best-fit with its confidence band, obtained assuming Baumgardt et al. (2023) mass function slope and theoretical BaSTI isochrones Hidalgo et al. (2018); Pietrinferni et al. (2021); Salaris et al. (2022); Pietrinferni et al. (2024) with 13 Gyr, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.4$, $Y = 0.247$ and metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ taken from the Harris (1996) catalog (2010 edition). The estimated parameters are given in Table 4.

Fig. B.4: Relation between the χ^2 test statistic of our fitting procedure in Sect. 3.1 with the average relative error on $\sigma(m)$ from Watkins et al. (2022).

Fig. B.5: Model prediction of the velocity dispersion as function of stellar mass for different values of Φ_0 (continuous lines with circles), compared to the complete equipartition limit (dashed lines with triangles). The plots are obtained averaging the dispersion radial profile in the core.